

KNOWLEDGE BASED ENGINEERING (KBE) AUTOMATIC LAYOUT GENERATION FRAMEWORK FOR MODULAR OFFSHORE WIND SERVICE VESSELS

I-Ting. Kao^{1,2} and Austin A. Kana¹

¹ Delft University of Technology, Delft, the Netherlands

² Fugro Marine Service B.V., Voorburg-Leidschendam, the Netherlands

Abstract. A significant debate persists on whether to design and build a new fleet specifically for offshore wind farm operations or retrofit existing offshore support vessels (OSVs) to enhance their capabilities. This research aims to propose a ship design method that enhances mission flexibility for offshore wind farm-related operations by refining the preliminary design phase. The two primary elements in constructing a Multi-Model Generator (MMG) for OSVs in this research are modularity and Knowledge Based Engineering (KBE). Modularity formed the base to decompose the complex ship system into multiple subsystems formed by function blocks. Each function block is a module that can be accessed by CAD software to reassemble a new vessel subsystem and integrate it into a new OSV design. KBE transfers a collection of modules into a functional system. In each system, there is a small group of essential elements for building a system, such as engines, shafts, and propellers in a propulsion system. These components are the High-Level Primitives (HLP) in a system. KBE aims to discover and utilize the potential of each HLP, forming them into meaningful configurations. The design results generated by the KBE system are visualized in a CAD system through the MMG application. The MMG demonstrates the ability to generate a modular OSV product family with a chosen parent hull while allowing parallel engineering work on the deck layout configuration. There is potential for future improvement by incorporating a well-constructed industry database. This method addresses the need for modular reconfiguration and the diversity of modules in OSV design, ultimately supporting the sustainable development of offshore wind farms.

Keywords: *Knowledge Based Engineering, Modularity, Multi-model generator, Early-stage ship design, Offshore wind support vessel*

1 Introduction

The boom in offshore wind farm construction has created a wave of prospective interest among ship builders [1]. Along with the opportunities, ship designers and operators have encountered a new era in designing and running novel offshore support vessel (OSV) fleets specifically to support offshore wind. However, there remain several challenges that ship operators need to account for, among which are: oversizing, overweight, and overperformance. This stems from the fact that these vessels were built to support the conventional oil industry but might not be suitable nor optimal for the work at an offshore wind farm [2]. From an engineering perspective, there are some similarities between the work procedures at an offshore wind farm and a petroleum extraction site, such as anchor positioning, ROV support, and construction unit deployment. However, offshore wind farms requires faster and more precise work, which can hardly be done by the huge platform support vessel involved in the oil industry [3]. An additional challenge for this market is to attract investors in the near future by providing them with supporting vessels at a lower price, delivered in a shorter time.

From the supply side, shipyards are looking for solutions to reduce design and construction time. A modularity-based approach is one of the ways being explored in the early design stages to help the industry transform from engineered-to-order to assemble-to-order business model [4]. Building OSV platforms as a modular product family allows shipyards to modify the basic design easily thus to achieve better cost efficiency. By dividing systems into functional modules, designers can explore model concepts tailored to customers' needs by swapping module

components within the same product family. One of the main questions in the modularity building principles is how to exactly define what a module is [5]. There are numerous ways to decompose the system: by function similarity, by structure continuity, or by class regulations [6]. These items are common initial input data. Then, the process begins by transforming previous design experiences into reusable knowledge and sorting it by methods, rules, heuristics, constraints, and guidelines related to their properties. The knowledge in the database then can be reused in new but similar product development [7].

This is exactly how to setup a Knowledge Based Engineering (KBE) system. It enables designers to focus more on the mission-oriented components while designing the whole platform system. With the shared modules stored in the database, reusing functional units can narrow down quickly to basic but reliable arrangements.

It is not enough to accelerate the design process by defining modules and set up the database. To better approach the conceptual design, automatically generated models in CAD software can help to find out several possible solutions to shorten the time from words in contract to first design [8]. By reusing the modules in the KBE database combined with previous general arrangement cases, it will facilitate the rapid exploration of configurations to support a product family. That is, an automatic generation algorithm has the potential to adopt the modularity concept under KBE structure to create a better solution for generating new offshore wind farm OSVs' general arrangement.

This paper proposes a framework for building a product family of the future offshore wind farm support vessels' with a common platform with different configuration according to their mission. The idea is to apply modularity principles to accelerate the processing of conceptual design. A KBE system is used to formalize the engineering data and to transform them into reusable engineering knowledge for bringing different modules together. From the dozens of designs generated by the KBE system by a single input, automatic model generator can assist designers to quickly focus on more rational designs according to the requirements.

2 Design Methodology

The objective of this research is to develop a method to design an offshore support vessel fleet with the intention to mitigate repetitive and iterative works throughout the ship design process. Modularization offers a structured approach to maintaining this knowledge, encompassing both the initiations and the results. The advantages of modularization include reducing system complexity, leveraging similarities, and generating variety. For each design generated in the 'define systems' phase, stakeholders can agree on a collection of operational equipment designed to perform within specified parameters, such as a particular weather window or target drilling depth. During the functional definition phase, a ship platform can be selected from existing designs on the market or generated from a parent hull. The separation of operational equipment and ship platform then enables the configure-to-order (CTO) strategy developed by Choi [9]. CTO is a bottom-up design approach in prototyping new designs by configuring modules predeveloped and stored in the database. The most obvious advantage is the availability to perform fast and accurate modeling result and thus to reduce the development time and cost [9]. A schematic flowchart to explain CTO strategy is provided in **Figure 1**.

Figure 1 Configure-to-order strategy for Ship design [9]

Compared to modularized equipment, the modular platform development received has less attention. Erikstad and Levander [6] mentioned that standard ship modules comprises main hull, deckhouse, bridge, tanks and voids.

These modules are designed and reconfigured to provide basic ship functions such as buoyancy, transition, storage, and accommodation. With this structure, a complex ship system is subdivided into a number of categories based on their functionality. Furthermore, modules in a single category shared a common base of knowledge such as machinery system in the machinery category or ship structure in the structure category. The last advantage for applying modularization is the ability to generate variety. The processor to select a collection of modules from each categories and put them into a corresponding position to make a reasonable design is the last puzzle of this research, which is the KBE system.

KBE is a branch of knowledge based system (KBS) developed in the artificial intelligence (AI) field dated back to 1970's. KBE is designed to solve multidisciplinary problems by rule-based reasoning process then perform the output in a computer assist design (CAD) software. It acts as a merger of artificial intelligence and CAD software as illustrated in **Figure 2**. KBE captures, structures and records knowledge of a complex system making it reusable, transferable and expandable. The primary aim of using KBE in design works is to reduce time and costs for engineering design by automating repetitive design tasks [10]. The process of breaking down a system into manageable blocks is similar to the process of modularization, where physical modules are represented by "virtual modules" [11] for product development and mass customization.

Figure 2 KBE systems: computer programs containing knowledge and reasoning mechanisms augmented by geometry handling capabilities to provide engineering design solutions [12]

For most of the KBE application in the ship design and ship building industries, the focus has been on structural design since the standards of steel works are well developed [13, 14, 15]. Conversely, in the aerospace industry, KBE tools are extensively used in concurrent aircraft design. The Design and Engineering Engine (DEE) is a product by leveraging the advantage of reasoning process of KBE and exporting the design result into CAD software for detailed analysis and initiate an optimization process. Here, requirements from the customers are transformed into the design parameter that can be processed by a software solver to initiate the preliminary design. For example, when considering only the capacity of payload and lifting force, the fuselage and wing are the critical factors. When looking at only the geometry, both wing and fuselage are "trunk-like" parts. When assigning the functionality to provide lifting force, the "trunk-like" part becomes a wing. On the other hand, a "trunk-like" part with capability to accommodate passengers and cargos becomes a fuselage. When assigning the same "trunk-like" part with both capability to take payload and to generate lifting force, a new concept airplane is then formed, namely the design similar to the B-12 Bomber or the Flying-V. These "trunk-like" parts in airplane design are defined as High Level Primitives (HLPs) by La Rocca [16]. HLPs capture a certain set of engineering knowledge for designing different part of an airplanes. For instance, a wing trunk HLP can be used to generate a (piece of) aircraft wing, vertical tail or aileron if assigned as an type of lifting surface.

To make design work more intuitive, a visualization of the design result is essential. A Multi Model Generator (MMG) is the bridge between script-based KBE system and graphic based CAD software. Constructed using Object Oriented Programming (OOP) enables the MMG to generate different concepts from various engineering initiation by leveraging the reasoning process in KBE [17]. The models exported from the MMG will be processed to further analysis. The analytical results will be the input of the optimization and qualification process until a converged design is generated which fulfilled all the requirements. In short, MMG pieces together different HLPs

to create concepts initiated with different engineering approaches. In this research, the objective is to develop a KBE-based MMG for developing OSV products. The new MMG is expected to:

- Generate different OSV configurations with self-defined HLPs
- Generate different working deck configurations according to different operations
- Display feasible hydrostatic performances

2.1 Mission and Functionality Design

2.1.1 Define Vessel Types

Offshore support vessels are specifically built to support offshore engineering sites, including traditional drilling platforms, Floating Production Storage and Offloading units, and offshore wind farm construction and operation. The high complexity and demand for up-to-date technology make the design of OSVs a challenge for naval architects [18]. A new offshore wind farm consists of four main stages: Pre-construction, Construction and Installation, Operation and Maintenance, and Decommissioning. Each stage requires a unique fleet to fulfill the tasks. According to the OECD [19], there are at least 17 types of vessels needed throughout the wind farm life cycle. Of these, the following ship types were selected as suitable candidates for the study, namely, Geographical/Geotechnical Survey Vessel, Diving Support Vessel, Cable Laying Vessel, Construction Support Vessel, and Multi-purpose Project/Cargo Vessel.

2.1.2 Define Hull Form

Compared to merchant ships, OSVs are relatively small in size and capacity. Since their missions are primarily at a fixed location, cargo capacity is not the main concern. Instead, the ability to operate in heavy weather is a crucial design driver for these vessels. Data on 100 OSVs have been individually collected and studied. Information about these vessels was sourced from ship design companies, shipyards, and offshore engineering service charters. Error! Reference source not found. and **Figure 4** compare the vessels recorded in Erikstad et al.'s research [6] with the reference vessels stored in the database built for this research.

Figure 3 OSV vessel Length-GT in the database comparing with the literature [6]

Figure 4 OSV vessel Width-GT in the database comparing with the literature [6]

Vessels specifications are analyzed from two main aspects: ship length and crew size. For ship length, a similar block coefficient (C_b) value can be adapted from similar vessel products to determine the main dimensions of the vessel. Crew size, on the other hand, will determine the deck area and required water storage. The former is compared with the data provided in Erikstad et al.'s research [6] and the latter is studied to validate the safety crew size for the final design of the research. The overall length and breadth result is provided in **Figure 5**. A group of similar ship lengths is located between 75 to 90 meters. The breadth ranges between 15 to 20 meters, which aligns with the results shown in **Figure 4** and **Figure 5**. There is a trend towards reducing crew size for new build vessels, and the crew size is expected to change according to new regulations.

Figure 5 Vessels specification L(LOL)-B

Figure 6 Crew size versus ship length

2.2 Modularity and Modularization

In this section, the modularization of an OSV system will be discussed. The procedure begins with a system breakdown into a number of subsystems. Subsystems are broken down further into components and configurations to perform specific functions. The components from each subsystem are expected to be a self-sufficient unit, known as module. There are two major groups of the modules: function modules (e.g., an engine in an engine room) and form modules (e.g., the bow section as part of the hull). Modules are defined by boundaries that encompass the whole system and components that need to be assembled to perform functions of the parent subsystem. For example, both a tube and a pump are components in a hydraulic system, but they are not a module until it is being assembled as a Hydraulic Power Unit (HPU). However, a subsystem is not functional with modules alone; the knowledge behind configurations is key to assembling the modules into a meaningful modular system. This research contains two different types of configuration formats which are layout configuration and form configuration.

2.2.1 System Function Breakdown

A system is formed by multiple subsystems and interacting elements. These subsystems are products that provide specific functions such as generating power, moving, maneuvering, navigating, transporting crew and cargo, drilling, investigating, and laying cables. These functions originate from customer requirements and are translated by ship designers into organized inputs for different systems, such as the power plant, drive chain, bridge, accommodation, and functional payloads. Adapting the SFI code and System-Based Ship Design (SBSD) process [20], the OSV system breakdown is shown in Figure 7. The colors for task-related systems in the diagram indicate the sections from which they originally come.

Figure 7 OSV System breakdown using SFI code

2.2.2 Subsystem modules and modular platform

The main driver for designing a modular platform is the method of accessing required functions. This approach significantly influences the structure of the modular system by defining what constitutes a "self-sufficient" module and the reasoning process for forming these modules into meaningful configurations. Take the main power plant system as an example. The boundary is the compartment of the main engine room, which contains the main engines, auxiliary engines, and main generator as modules and they are positioned at the strengthened point of the hull structure. Ideally, each subsystem can be treated as an independent modular platform with several modules to perform a certain function, similar to Legos on a base plate. However, some subsystems require more than one boundary box because they are divided into a storage space and an operation space. For instance, the fuel storage and supplying system is divided into main fuel storage tanks and daily fuel tanks. A detailed system component list with physical boundaries, building blocks, and modules is provided in **Table 1**.

Table 1 Modular subsystems derived from OSV system (*This is a mix modularity **This item will be elaborated by ship types in the complexity managing section)

System	Physical Boundary	Blocks	Modules
Main power plant system	Main engine room	Main engine room	Main engine Auxiliary engine Main generator
Technical space	Technical space	Changing room Garage	Auxiliary outfitting Leather machine
Fore Mooring system	Fore mooring deck	Fore mooring deck	Mooring winch Spare anchor
Bow thruster system	Bow thruster room	Bow thruster room	Bow thruster
Water Ballast system	Side water ballast tank(s) Bottom water ballast tank(s)	Side water ballast tank(s) Bottom water ballast tank(s)	Pump Sounding device *Coating system
Stabilization system	Anti-Rolling Tank(s)	Anti-Rolling Tank(s)	Pump Sounding device
Fuel storage and supplying system	Main fuel storage Tank(s) Day fuel tank(s)	Main fuel storage Tank(s) Daily fuel tank(s)	Fuel treating system
Lube oil storage and supplying system	Lube oil storage Tank(s) Service lube oil tank(s)	Lube oil storage Tank(s) Service lube oil tank(s)	Lube oil treating system
Cargo hold	Cargo hold	Cargo hold	Liquid cargo containers Special cargo containers
Propulsion system	Aft engine room	Aft engine room	Motor ShaftPod thruster
Task related and reserved space	Diving support room Diving control room	Moon Pool Diving support room Diving control room	Gas storage Saturation vessel Office furniture
Task related systems	Weather/Working deck	Stern roller	**Task related modules

2.2.3 Modular OSV platform

The modular OSV platform can be subdivided into two modular platform groups: the hull, which provides buoyancy, and the system, which provides functions. Each group requires a different reasoning process to be assembled and ultimately integrated into a modular OSV. After defining the physical boundary and the modules, the next step is to establish the reasoning system for constructing these two modular platforms.

Form configuration focuses on the hull design and the modular platform contained in each hull section. An OSV is defined as a floating structure capable of sailing in offshore areas at a designed speed and maintaining stability while performing offshore operations. Therefore, a hull structure is generally a type of floating structure with an optimized shape for better hydrodynamic performance, providing sufficient stability in the offshore area. The hull structure can be further described as a vessel object formed with three parts: Fore hull, Mid hull, and Aft hull. Different hull structures are listed in **Figure 8**. In this case, hull parts are the physical boundary while the functional compartments are the modules and sub modular platform.

Figure 8 Types of floating structure configurations

Layout configuration focus on clarifying the connection between modules and put them on a relative position within the physical boundary to make the modular platform functional. The boundary of the systems are the operational decks, or a specific compartment and the modules are mainly modularized equipment.

Figure 9 Types of Equipment Layout

2.2.4 Modularization of OSV System

The main idea of this section is to demonstrate how to decompose the OSV system into a compact and self-sufficient system. It applies the SBSD methodology to make the OSV system a parent modular platform (the vessel), which consists of two modular platform groups with different configuration processes. The hull of the OSV is formed by the form configuration to meet the hydrodynamic and hydrostatic requirements of an OSV. Ship systems and operation-related systems are formed using the layout configuration to meet the operational and ship system requirements.

2.3 Knowledge Based Engineering

In this section, the modular OSV platform structure will be reshaped to fit into the proposed Object-Oriented Programming (OOP) structure. This will serve as a guideline for developing a KBS. Along with the MMG, a KBE-like framework can be established.

2.3.1 Object-Oriented modular OSV Model Framework Development

The modules and modular platform defined in the previous section provide an information storage structure suitable for access by a program-based processor. Modular platforms can be described as knowledge blocks containing attributes of objects and codes for interactions between objects. These blocks store engineering information in a standardized data structure, transforming it into "knowledge." This knowledge can be accepted, analyzed, and reused by the computer, thereby initiating the automation and optimization process. When integrating these knowledge blocks into a design, an OOP approach is suitable for ensuring the engineering results adhere to optimization directions. By defining one or multiple components as major optimization objects, the processor generates a series of designs that meet the design requirements.

To develop an OOP program, a class diagram in Unified Modeling Language (UML) is used to illustrate the connections between modular platform groups and modules. An example of OSV system in a class diagram is provided in **Figure 10**. In the diagram, the modular OSV platform is defined by a series of aggregates and functions and is set as the final design object. The HLP-connection is a type of form module and also as a modular platform contains of a number of compartment modules. These compartment modules also serve as the boundaries for the layout configuration modular platform. With the class diagram, the modular OSV platform secures the ability to be expanded for future development and can be accessed as internal knowledge library for engineering experiences.

Figure 10 Class diagram of a modular OSV platform

2.3.2 High Level primitive

HLPs are the most essential components of the whole modular OSV platform. An HLP is a basic unit of a product that contains a certain amount of knowledge, including attributes and operations. The final product is a collection of HLPs with certain inputs to generate a product at the right position with the right size. Two sets of HLPs serve for either the hull form modular platform or layout configuration.

The first type of hull form HLPs is a mimic of CAD application. It is defined as the basic element for designing the hull shape of a modular OSV. Hull form HLPs contain information as position, vector, length, and curve blend types (attributes) and are assigned with different typical functions (operation). **Figure 11** shows an example of the Hull form HLP. The ForeHull-like HLP is a special shaped floating structure that is installed on an OSV. By changing the design requirements, the HLP can transform into at least four bow shape in the OSV market. Functions provided by this ForeHull-like HLP can be housing for main engines, mooring systems, DP system and garage for operation vehicles. Five hull HLPs are defined in this research which are: ForeHull-like block, MidHull-like block, AftHull-like block, Superstructure-like block, and a supportive Connection block.

Figure 11 ForeHull-like block variants and its' function assemblies

The second type of layout configuration HLPs adapted the concept from the factory layout applications. In this case, HLPs are individual modular equipment that form a functional layout following certain rules and relationships. Each HLP contains basic dimension information (attributes) and functional information (operation). This layout will be validated by the classification rules to show whether it satisfied the safety requirement. **Figure 12** shows an example of the application of this type of HLP. On a Cable Laying Vessel, four major modular equipment are set as HLP blocks. However, these pieces of modular equipment must be placed according to certain rules to perform the storage of cables, the handling of cables, and the deployment of the cables. In this research, HLPs are created for Geo-Survey vessel, Diving Support vessel, Construction Support vessel, and Cable laying vessel.

Figure 12 Modular equipment as HLPs in a layout (CLV working deck as an example)

2.3.3 Verification criteria

After a proposed engineering result is reached, a series of formula are used to verify the design.

Initial Stability

From the definition [21], metacentric height (GM) can be calculated by applying the following equations:

$$GM = KB + BM - KG \quad (1)$$

$$BM = I/V \quad (2)$$

$$KG = \frac{W_{hull} * Z_{center\ of\ volume} + W_{OperationDeck} * Z_{deck}}{W_{Hull} + W_{OperationDeck}} \quad (3)$$

The KG value is estimated by taking the weights of the hull and working deck layout into account. For achieving a more practical GM value, the value 2.5m from literature [22] is suggested by a ship designer and chosen to be the goal of the design value. This standard is higher than the minimum requirement of 0.15 m suggested by DNV-GL [23].

Weight Estimation

Weight estimation is approached from two aspects. The first one is from the theoretical aspect adapting the empirical and semi-empirical methods introduced in Watson's publication [24].

$$W_{si} = K_{si} * E^{1.36} \quad (4)$$

$$W_s = W_{si} * [1 + 0.05(C'_b - 0.70)] \quad (5)$$

$$C'_b = C_b + (1 - C_b) * (0.8D - T)/(3T) \quad (6)$$

$$W_{machinery} = 12 * \left(\frac{MCR}{RPM}\right)^{0.84} \quad (7)$$

$$W_{remainder} = K_{remainder} * MCR^{0.70} \quad (8)$$

$$W_{electric} = 0.72 * MCR^{0.78} \quad (9)$$

$$\sum W_{Hull} = W_s + W_{machinery} + W_{remainder} + W_{electric} + W_{OperationDeck} \quad (10)$$

$$Deckloading = W_{OperationDeck}/A_{WorkingDeck} \quad (11)$$

Where:

- W_{si} : Steel-weight at $C_b' = 0.70$ as plotted/lifted from graph
- E : 1300 (Offshore Supply and Research ship) [24]
- K_{si} : 0.045 [24]
- W_s : Steel-weight for actual C_b' at 0.8D
- $K_{remainder}$: 0.19 (frigate)
- $Deckloading$: 7 Ton/m² [23]

The result provides a rough estimate of the steel weight for the entire ship. The sum of the estimated weights offers an approximation of the primary deadweight. This rough calculation demonstrates that the MMG can perform a weight estimation. However, it cannot be directly referenced as the actual weight of the vessel. The purpose is to indicate how much additional payload can be accommodated on board. In addition to the difference between the two weight values, deck loading is also considered to ensure a feasible result.

Power Estimation

$$R_{Total} = C_T * 0.5 * \rho * V_s^2 * S \quad (12)$$

$$P_E^{def} = R_T * V_s = T * V_s \quad (13)$$

$$P_B = \frac{P_E}{\eta_D * \eta_{TRM}} * EM * SM \quad (14)$$

Where:

- R_{Total} : total resistance
- ρ : density of seawater
- V_s : ship speed
- C_T : 0.001-0.005 [25]
- T : Thrust
- EM : 0.85
- SM : 1.1

Installed power estimation is based on the empirical methods introduced by Klein Woud and Stapersma [26]. The result provides the required installed power to meet the designed ship speed, maximum ship speed and bollard pull for tugboats.

2.3.4 KBE data structure for modular OSV system

In this section, the knowledge contained in a modular OSV system is structured by applying two sets of HLPs, with their connections illustrated in a class diagram. **Figure 13** shows a big map of the entire system structure of the data structure. The OOP program is expected to select HLPs from the pool by assigning the required mission layout and the expected form, then provide a series of design results. These designs will undergo a series of checks to ensure they meet basic ship design criteria.

Figure 13 KBE structure of a modular OSV system

2.4 Multi-model Model Generator

To enable real-time monitoring of changes in the modeling results, a platform that offers both programming flexibility and an intuitive demonstration of modeling results is preferable. Rhinoceros 6-Grasshopper is the selected development package, as it is widely used for architectural modeling. Additionally, it includes Python and C frameworks for building OOP directly within the MMG. Therefore, it has been chosen as the main development tool for the MMG in this research.

2.4.1 Hull modeling

The three steps for creating the shell of ship hulls are (Figure 14):

1. Generate front and after section line.
2. Place sweeping rails and intermediate section lines.
3. Generate the surface by sweeping the section lines along the rails.
4. Close the openings

Figure 14 hull-like block construction

The following provides more details of the input for each block. The variables for defining the hull are adapted from [8] and are modified according to [27] and Koning's [28]. To reduce the confusion in naming objects, a unified naming rule is applied:

1. **Mid_Hull_line_A**: This is the Aft-section line. Since the MidHull block is the first built section for prototyping, the name is inherited by the later designed sections.
2. **Mid_Hull_line_F**: This is the Fore-section line. At ForeHull, it defines the bow shape. At MidHull, it defines the start of the MidHull. At Stern, it defines the start of stern.
3. **line_maindeck_CL**: This is the center line of the main deck. Together with the keel center line define the surface for mirroring the port-side to starboard side.
4. **line_bilge_t**: This is the bilge top line. It defines the start of the bilge. At the ForeHull, it defines the chine.
5. **line_bilge_b**: This is the bilge bottom line. It defines the start of the flatbottom.
6. **line_keel_CL**: This is the keel line.
7. **line_trans #_p**: This is the section control line. It locks the edges curvature and vector of each hull block to ensure a smooth connection.

The endpoints of each line are control points on the ship hull, which generate a rough shape of the hull by importing their XYZ values. Users can also create a new hull shape by starting with a parent hull. Two ship hulls with different designs are used as modeling examples. Both hulls are generated using the basic MMG shell function. The first hull is based on the specifications of the reference vessel, BOKA Sherpa [29] is shown in **Figure 15**. This model includes two shell objects: ForeHull-like block and AftHull-like block.

Figure 15 Conventional Ship model (Aft+connection(thin)+Fore)

The second hull replicates the reference vessel, BOKA Da VINCI [30] is shown in **Figure 16**. This model comprises four shell objects: ForeHull-like block, Connection block, MidHull-like block, and AftHull-like block. It is characterized by a bulbous bow and a gradually tapering stern.

Figure 16 Bulb-like Ship model (Aft+Connection(compartment)+Mid+Fore)

2.4.2 Compartment modeling

After assembling the HullForm blocks, the next step is to generate the compartment enclosed by the hull form. To minimize interaction with the shell object, an internal boundary is required to define the actual functional space within the hull, excluding the wing and bottom tanks.

The wing and bottom tanks are chosen to define this boundary based on the author's experience with various reference vessels and block division plans. The default function of the bottom tank is assigned as bottom ballast tanks. For the wing tank, there is no default function; it can either be thin like a steel plate or spacious enough to serve as a walkway, depending on the user's input. Examples from three different vessels are provided in **Figure 17**.

Figure 17 Examples of Wing (red) and Bottom (blue) tank layout in three different vessel (BOKA DA VINCI, BOKA SHERPA, FOCAL 532 90M RDSV)

The procedure for creating this internal boundary is illustrated in **Figure 18**. Details for each step:

1. Project line_bilge_t to the center surface to create a reference line line_bilge_CL
2. Extrude line_bilge_t to line_bilge_CL to generate the tank top deck.
3. Close the openings to form a ClosedBrep to represent the bottom tank. The top surface of the bottom tank is the bottom boundary of the wing tank surface.
4. Extrude the side shell to defined length to generate the wing tank.
5. Mirror the two ClosedBrep objects according to the centerline to create symmetric tanks on the starboard side.
6. Take all the corners of the inner space to create the boundary box.
7. This boundary box's dimension is adjustable afterward by changing the width of the wing tank.

Figure 18 Construction of Boundary Box

The boundary box separates the shell generator and internal layout generator into individual systems. This separation allows for parallel processing of hull design and internal system design. Users first define the height of the tank top and the width of the wing tanks by entering the value to the MMG. The concept is demonstrated using the main dimensions of the reference vessel BOKA Da Vinci, as shown in **Figure 19**. The model identifies three main sections with different functions. The boundary of the functional compartment is defined by the bulkhead shared with the ForeHull-like Block. This boundary box concept is applied to the Midhull-like block, Stern-like block, and Connection block.

Figure 19 Assembly boundary box construction result

2.4.3 Deck Plan modeling

With the newly defined boundaries, the next step is to build the deck plan. In this section, the modified Midhull-like block, Stern-like block, and Forehull-like block are chosen as the objects. Based on the functions assigned to this HLP listed in 2.3.2, it is assumed that the Midhull-like section is constructed with "box-like" assemblies such as Fuel Oil Tank (F.O.T), Lubricating Oil Tank (L.O.T), Fresh Water Tank (F.W.T), liquid cargo tank, and an optional tunnel passage to connect the bow and stern.

Figure 20 outlines the procedure to generate an internal layout for a similar tank:

1. Create the floor of each assembly.
2. Extrude it to the defined height.
3. Close all openings and ensure all blocks are "Close-Brep".
4. (Optional) Create the cross-section of the tunnel passage.
5. (Optional) Extrude the section along the path to generate a box.
6. (Optional) Use BooleanDifference to create the tunnel.

Figure 20 Construction of deck plan configuration

Modeling results for the MidHull and AftHull are provided in **Figure 21**. The tunnel passage is created using BooleanDifference to ensure the system continuously records the enclosed volume of all tanks in this section. The red and green boxes in the Stern-like block are designated as propulsion rooms, reserved for installing either direct drive from the propulsion machinery or azimuth thrusters. The connection-block HLP is assigned either as a functional compartment or cargo hold, resulting in an internal layout that essentially fills all the space enclosed by the boundary box.

Figure 21 Deck plan configuration inside a MidHull-like block and a SternHull-like block

After the hull form construction from MidHull to SternHull, next steps are to model compartments enclosed by Forehull-like block. Since the Forehull-like block is the section with the most diverse shape.

In **Figure 22** shows an example of how this concept is deployed.

1. Create the boundary to separate the fore- and aft section of the ForeHull section. This boundary is different from the curve "line_trans2_p" to define the shape as mentioned earlier in the hull shape generating part.
2. Define the deck height of the "1st-deck".
3. Use "BooleanSplit" to Split the "closedBrep".
4. Check all four breps are "closed-brep". This is important for a fail-created brep will invert the "BooleanSplit" result and switch the defined engine room and bow thruster room.

Figure 22 Deck plan configuration inside a ForeHull-like block

2.4.4 Super Structure Modeling

The superstructure is designed as a movable object generated according to the user defined longitudinal length, floor height, and deformation ratio at the x-axis. It is aimed to create a full breadth structure that changing the shape according to the deck line. The concept for building this object follows the steps in **Figure 23**:

Figure 23 Construction of Superstructure block

1. Extract the deck line from the shell object.
2. Create the aft- and fore boundary of the superstructure.
3. Sweep along the deck line from aft to the fore boundary to form the floor of the superstructure.
4. Move the floor along the deck line to the desired position. In this step, users can check whether a kink appears. The continuity check can also be done at the same time.
5. Extrude the floor with the assigned deck height. (The floor and ceiling shapes can be adjusted independently)

A completed superstructure example is provided in **Figure 24**

Figure 24 Example of a superstructure block

2.4.5 Layout Configuration Generator

The layout configuration generator is the second type of KBE employed. The process can be described as "create-scale-move-extrude". A schematic diagram is provided in **Figure 25**.

Figure 25 Construction of layout configuration generator

The target plane is divided into three sections: port-side, centerline, and starboard-side. For certain objects that must be placed close to the superstructure (e.g., a conditioned deck) or at the stern (e.g., a stern roller), the plane can be further subdivided into the forepart and aft part. The reference point for moving objects on the target plane is defined by the section to which they belong. This setup helps reduce user confusion regarding the y-direction values that should be assigned.

The logic for building the input data follows the order of centerline, port-side, and starboard-side, making it easier to place objects. Other objects are positioned according to their relationship matrix. The layout configuration generator adapts the pre-defined physical boundaries from the hull form. Users can import deck layout with a CSV file that indicates the parameters of objects, the number of objects and the required floor areas. Templates and rules are coded into the layout configuration generator to produce a conventional deck layout. Users can then modify the configuration according to reality. This configuration generator will be used to create layout configurations in compartments and on the operational deck. **Figure 26** shows layout examples in a diving support compartment and on the operational deck for different OSV types.

Figure 26 Result of layout Configuration

2.4.6 Whole Ship design

This section outlines the complete process for building the MMG. Following the OOP and class-diagram structure, the framework construction procedures are: "point-curve-surface-box" for the floating structure HLP in hull shell generation, and "shape-scale-place-arrange" for the modules HLP in the layout. This approach results in an effective modeling tool capable of reproducing previous design results, provided a formalized and standardized database is available. **Figure 27** illustrates a full model that incorporates all the features of a DSV from the reference ship database.

The Rhinoceros-Grasshopper combination allows users to see modifications made in the input sheet directly reflected in the model. Small adjustments to the model are also possible, as the parameters for building each section remain accessible through the Grasshopper interface. Finally, the MMG system has proven to provide a reliable

modeling result that is ready for testing. Results from reproducing several reference ships will be discussed to validate the modeling results.

Figure 27 Modular OSV platform generated DSV model

3 Results

The design criteria are established to validate the final design results. The mission equipment criteria will be used to check the deck capacity from both area and loading perspectives.

3.1 Validation of Models

3.1.1 BOKA DA VINCI

BOKA DA VINCI is a 12,565-ton diving support vessel equipped with both surface and saturation diving facilities certified by DNV-GL. The most important feature is the modularized saturation diving facility, which is integrated into the ship's structure. This facility includes two moonpools at the bottom level and a set of saturation vessels. In addition to the diving facility, the large capacity for fuel and water enables her to perform missions of longer duration.

From the system breakdown, the vessel needs to provide saturation and surface diving functions, ROV support, carrying deck cargo, and basic hotel and ship services. Therefore, the MidHull, AftHull, ForeHull, and Superstructure are chosen to form this vessel.

By running the MMG, a reproduction of the vessel is generated. The characteristics of the vessel and the comparison with the reference vessel are provided in **Figure 28**. The difference in displacement is less than 2 percent. As a model generated with only the main dimensions, the result can be considered satisfactory. The total installed power is difficult to estimate as most of the energy consumption remains unknown at the moment. However, the estimation of the required power for propulsion is highly accurate. The forecastle floor is overestimated by around 200 m² due to the inclusion of conditioned deck area. The crew number is underestimated because some accommodation compartments are located under the main deck. The superstructure area is distributed to crews, with 7 m² per person according to MLC rules for vessels over 10,000 tons.

Figure 28 BOKA DA VINCI generated from modular OSV platform

3.1.2 BOKA SOVEREIGN

BOKA SOVEREIGN is a medium-sized sea-going tug boat that also provides anchor handling services. This vessel was chosen for validation to demonstrate that the MMG can handle smaller vessels and provide a satisfactory bollard pull power estimation. From the system breakdown, this vessel provides towing and anchor handling services, requires higher speed, and has a direct drive from the fore engine room. Therefore, the AftHull, ForeHull, and Superstructure are chosen to form this vessel.

The characteristics of the vessel and the comparison with the reference vessel are provided in **Figure 29**. The DWT of this vessel is not provided; thus, the most important feature in this table is the estimation of bollard pull power. It is estimated at the design bollard pull force of 195 tons at 0.1 knots. The freshwater tank does not meet the requirement because most voids in the stern section are categorized as fuel tanks. The real tank arrangement is not available from the datasheet, so there could be hidden voids for freshwater storage. Except for this defect, the other numerical results correspond highly to the reference vessel.

Figure 29 BOKA SOVEREIGN generated from modular OSV platform

3.2 Modular OSV product family

The second part of the modular platform development is performed. This is to show the impact of different operational configurations installed on the working deck. A positive GM is the main indication. In the real cases,

payloads on the working deck will elevate the position of COG. The value of GM will correspondingly decrease as the result. In this section, a process showing that BOKA Da Vinci's Hull is chosen to be the base of an OSV modular product family. It is now carrying different operational configurations to perform various operations including cable laying, Geo-physical/technical survey, and platform supply.

3.2.1 CSV LAYOUT

The CSV configuration is adapted from the BOKA SOVEREIGN. It includes an anchor handling winch, a towing winch guide pin, a shark jaw, and a roller. This configuration meets the requirements for handling the anchoring of wind farm foundations and deploying buoys as sea markers. The anchor handling winch provides continuous pulling force to ensure the anchor falls at a constant speed. The guide pin and shark jaw on the deck keep the chain centered to prevent it from sweeping across the deck. The empty areas on the deck are reserved for storing spare anchors and buoys. These areas can also be used for deck cargo when necessary. The proposed equipment list and model are provided in **Figure 30**. The GM is estimated to be 4.69 meters. Equipment weight estimations are sourced from ship outfitting providers. The deck loading is 0.19 tons per square meter. The vessel can accommodate at least 10 offshore anchors, each with a nominal weight of 30,000 kg from Fendercare Marine®. The remaining deck area can be used for carrying deck cargo or mounted with containerized equipment. The loading position of cargo can be generated from the configuration layout generator.

Technical specification_CSV			
Specification			Layout
GM	(m)	4.69	Anchor Handling Winch
Deck Capacity	(ton)	3,087	Guide Pin
SuperStructure_Helideck			Towing Winch
Deck No.		2	Shark Jaw
Helideck Radius		11	Stern Roller

Figure 30 Modular Platform - CSV

3.2.2 GSV LAYOUT

The GSV configuration is a type of vessel designed for geo-physical and geo technical survey. In this case, a geo-physical model is generated with the modular OSV platform. The proposed equipment list and model are provided in **Figure 31**. Equipment weight estimations are either adapted from other vessels or directly calculated based on box dimensions and mild steel density. The equipment includes a towed array sonar (TELEDYNE MARINE®-BENTHOS) and its Launch and Recovery System (LARS, estimated), sea drill rigs (MARUM®-MeBo70 drill rig), and a containerized lab (GeoTech®). The GM is estimated to be 5.4 meters. The spare area on the working deck can be used to carry cargo and samples from the seafloor.

Technical specification_GSV			
Specification			Layout
GM	(m)	5.4	Towed Array Sonar
Deck Capacity	(ton)	3,266	Towed Array Sonar LARS
SuperStructure_Helideck			Containerized Lab
Deck No.		2	Sea Drill Rig
Helideck Radius		11	

Figure 31 Modular Platform GSV

3.2.3 CLV LAYOUT

CLV is the heaviest configuration among all configurations. The proposed equipment list and model are provided in **Figure 32**. A cable storage facility is necessary for transporting cables to the designated location. Typically, an auxiliary crane is positioned on the side of the storage to lift the end of the wire and feed it into the tensioner. The wire is then stretched in the tensioner and attached to the trencher. After lowering the trencher to the seabed, the cable laying work is performed either by ship movement or automated trencher operation. A full cable laying facility is adapted from a commercial charting company (Drammen Offshore Leasing[®]). The trencher model, Deep Dig-It from Van Oord[®], is used. The GM is estimated to be 2.44 meters.

Figure 32 Modular Platform CLV

3.2.4 MPV Layout

The MPV vessel adapts the configuration of a DAMEN-designed service operations vessel [31]. It is designed to provide various offshore support operations, including crew transportation and offshore fleet supplementation. The proposed equipment list and model are provided in **Figure 33**. The Walk-2-Work module adapts the Ampelmann[®] A-type specification. The crane specification is adapted from the same crane used in the DSV model. Three deck cargoes with maximum loading capacity are also provided. The GM is calculated to be 4.7 meters. Deck loading is 2.39 tons per square meter. The spare deck area is reserved for additional deck cargo.

Figure 33 Modular Platform MPV

4 Conclusion

The final output of this research is an MMG designed for offshore windfarm service OSVs. It has been proven to generate various modular vessel platforms that reproduce models of reference vessels. Additionally, the modular platform, chosen as the base of a modular product family, has been developed to form a complete offshore service fleet by switching the working deck configuration.

One of the goals of this research was to identify HLPs for each subsystem. Three types of HLPs were provided and applied in the design of an OSV product family: HLP-Shell to represent the assemblies of the modular platform, HLP-Boundary box to represent the assemblies of ship sections, and HLP modules to generate functional layouts installed in different compartments, making them functional parts. Each HLP has its own attributes and operations stored in a class-structured database, which can be reused, resized, and rearranged to form new products within the product family.

The main advantage of the tool is its ability to accelerate the design process at the preliminary design stage. The MMG enables rapid generation of prototype designs, including primary design results such as GM, displacement, and propulsion power. With this basic information indicating the modular platform's performance, customers can quickly make decisions regarding the platform and proceed to the design of operation-related modules.

This MMG is actively used in the internal evaluation of the operational performance of different vessels within the Fugro research fleet when operating with Fugro-designed geotechnical and geophysical equipment as shown in **Figure 34**.

Figure 34 MMG being used in Fugro for studying operation performance

Acknowledgements

This work was performed as part of the academic thesis for the main author [32]. The authors would like to thank TU Delft for their support of this research. A special thanks to Austin Kana for his unwavering support throughout this project. The authors also extend their gratitude to Fugro Marine Service B.V. for their support of this paper.

5 References

- [1] W. Huang. Offshore windfarm growth could offer a lifeline to the OSV market. 209. [Online]. Available: <https://www.rivieramm.com/opinion/opinion/offshore-wind-farm-growth-could-offer-a-lifeline-to-the-osv-market-56041>.
- [2] C. Rex. Shipping market review. Danmarks Skibskredit, 2018.
- [3] I. Edwards. Overcoming challenges for the offshore wind industry and learning from the oil and gas industry. Report from POWER cluster, Natural Power and the Interreg IVB North Sea Region Programme, 2011.
- [4] B. O. H. J. & O. E. S. T. Representing design knowledge in configuration-based ship design. In *Comput 2008 - 7th International Conference on Computer and IT Applications in Maritime Industries*, 2008.
- [5] H. Tvedt. Modular approach to offshore vessel design and configuration, 2012.
- [6] Erikstad, S. O., Levander, K. System based design of offshore support vessels, 2012.
- [7] H. V. Devaraja. Knowledge based engineering (tech. rep.). Infosys, 2018.

- [8] N. Charisi. Parametric modelling method based on knowledge based engineering. TU Delft, 2019.
- [9] M. Choi. Modular adaptable ship design for handling uncertainty in the future operating context. Norwegian University of Science and Technology, 2018.
- [10] Cooper, S., Fan, I., & Li, G. Achieving competitive advantage through knowledge based engineering - a best practice guide, 2001.
- [11] Anderson, D., & Pine, J. *Agile product development for mass customization*. McGrawHill, 1997.
- [12] G. L. Rocca. Knowledge based engineering: Between AI and CAD. Review of a language based technology to support engineering design. *Advanced Engineering Informatics*, 2012, pp. 159-179.
- [13] Guan Guan; Qu Yang. Design and Optimization for Ship Structure Based on Knowledge-Based Engineering. In *SNAME*, 2018.
- [14] Michael Zimmermann; Robert Bronsart. A System for Management and Application of Standards in Ship Structural Design. In *SNAME*, 2007.
- [15] Tufail Shahzad, Peng Wang, Peter Van Lith, Jacques Hoffmans. Artificial Intelligence (AI) and Knowledge-Based Engineering (KBE) in Ship Design: Bridging Tradition and Technology Through ACQUAINT. *Journal of Ship Production and Design*, vol. 41, no. Society of Naval Architects and Marine Engineers, pp. 1-13, 2024.
- [16] G. L. Rocca. Knowledge based engineering techniques to support aircraft design and optimization. TU Delft, 2011.
- [17] Gianfranco La Rocca, Michel J.L. van Tooren. Knowledge based engineering to support aircraft multidisciplinary design and optimisation. In *26th International Congress of the Aeronautical Sciences*, 2008.
- [18] Ship design and construction, the society of naval architects and marine engineers. *SNAME*, 2003.
- [19] L. Daniel. Offshore vessel, mobile offshore drilling unit & floating production unit. OECD, 2014.
- [20] K. Levander. Innovative ship design-can innovative ships be designed in a methodological way. In *Proc. 8th Int. Marine Design Conference-IMDC03*, 2003.
- [21] A. Papanikolaou. *Ship design methodologies of preliminary design*. Springer, 2020
- [22] W. Wawrzynski. Area of the unstable solution of rolling equation– jumps of the oscillations amplitude. *Journal of KONES Powertrain and Transport*, 2018.
- [23] *Rules for classification ships part 5 ship types chapter 10 vessels for special operations*. DNV-GL, 2020.
- [24] D. Watson. *Practical ship design*. Elsevier Science, 1998.
- [25] L. Birk. *Fundamentals of ship hydrodynamics: Fluid mechanics, ship resistance and propulsion*. John Wiley Sons Ltd, 2019.
- [26] Woud, J. K., & Stapersma, D. *Design of propulsion and electric power generation systems*. IMarEST, 2018.
- [27] F. M. Sanches. Parametric modelling of hull form for ship optimization. Tecnico Lisboa, 2016.
- [28] J. H. Koning. Development of a KBE application to support aerodynamic design and analysis. TU Delft, Delft, 2010.
- [29] *Boka Sherpa*. Boskalis, 2020.
- [30] *Boka Da Vinci*. Boskalis, 2020.
- [31] Bibby Wavemaster. DAMEN, 2017.
- [32] I.-T. KAO. Knowledge Based Engineering (KBE) automatic layout generation framework for modular offshore wind service vessels. TU Delft, Delft, 2021.
- [33] J.J. H. Evans. Basic design concepts. In *Journal of the American Society for Naval Engineers*, WILEY, 1959, pp. 671-678.
- [34] Schut, E., & van Tooren, M. Engineering primitives to reuse design process knowledge. In *Conference Proceedings*, 2008.
- [35] F. Z. Rebecca Williams. GLOBAL OFFSHORE WIND Report. In *GWEC Conference*, 2024.